

TECHNOLOGY FOR ASSESSMENT OF THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF PROFESSORS-TEACHERS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASE OF INDICATORS OF STUDENTS' SATISFACTION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes ways to improve the quality of educational services in higher educational institutions, in particular, improving the system of critical performance indicators (KPI) in improving the activities of teaching staff. On this basis, a technology for assessing the professional activities of university teachers based on student satisfaction indicators is proposed. Latent factors for assessing the professional activities of professors and teachers have been developed.*

Keywords: *educational environment of the university, student satisfaction, students, university reputation, pedagogical knowledge and culture, teaching skills, student support, assessment of student knowledge.*

Today, the quality of education is becoming a factor determining the level of the development of society, in particular, the social well-being of the population, the economic development of the country, and the level of human capital. In particular, the level of human capital depends on the level of the quality of educational services in higher education, as well as the level of knowledge and culture of professors and teachers who determine the quality of educational services, pedagogical skills. According to Lee Kuan Yew, who created the "Miracle of Singapore", the people who made "miracles" in the country are teachers [1].

Evaluating the activities of professors and teachers is one of the ways to improve the quality of educational services for any higher education institution. In this regard, the opinions of students who are direct consumers of educational services and their satisfaction indicators are important.

It allows monitoring the satisfaction of students with the educational environment in higher education institutions, increasing the quality of education and identifying important points for improving the professional activity of professors and teachers.

In many developed countries of the world, in particular, in the USA[2,3], Singapore[4], England[5], Italy[6] and Ireland[7], the professional activity of professors and teachers is measured by "student satisfaction" and "Students' commitment to HE" evaluation by criteria, researches are being carried out on the scientific justification of these criteria. Also, Z.Allam and M.Iacovidou's research found that there is a relationship between the level of knowledge and culture of professors and the quality of education and students' satisfaction with higher education institutions [8,9].

The researches of CIS scientists I.A.Dagayva, V.V.Bakhotsky, L.I. Strikunova studied ways of increasing the attractiveness of HEIs by diagnosing students' satisfaction with the educational environment. According to them, the satisfaction of students is influenced not only by the educational environment, teaching methods, but also by the attitude towards the student

personality, information about professors and teachers (scientific potential, achievements, research directions) has a secret [10].

In our country, studies on the evaluation of the activity of professors and teachers and the determination of the most important performance indicators (KPI) are being carried out from the point of view of improving the management of HEIs. In particular, it was noted in the studies that the KPI system does not meet the same standards, it is considered more effective to implement it based on the characteristics of HEIs, regions, countries, as well as the approaches used in the practice of teacher evaluation processes are not based on transparent calculations, technological processes are not sufficiently substantiated, etc. In some cases, the evaluation of the information and the results of the work performed is determined to have a subjective and incomprehensible nature [Askarov].

The use of criteria related to the level of student satisfaction in evaluating the professional activity of professors and teachers in higher education institutions creates conditions for the realization of latent factors that cannot be determined in the KPI system. In particular, the current KPI systems do not allow to evaluate such important components as the knowledge and culture of the professor-teacher, pedagogical skills, attitudes towards the assessment of students' knowledge level, and support for students' educational needs and initiatives.

Today, it is appropriate to recognize some factors and characteristics that affect the quality of education in higher education institutions of our country.

According to interviews conducted with first-year students admitted to HEIs, the main goal of most of them was to enter higher education institutions. In order to achieve this goal, he attended educational centers and private tutoring courses together with education from general schools. According to observations, after being admitted to the studentship (achieving the goal), relaxation processes occur in them in relation to education for a certain period of time, as a result, the educational results are not sufficiently monitored in the 1st year, which is considered a propaedeutic stage.

According to the analysis of the experiences of foreign HEIs on quality assurance in higher education, the main components of improving the quality of education have been recognized. Based on this, we present the following components of improving the quality of education:

1. Learners. The goal and need of students for education is the most important component of ensuring the quality of education.

2. The reputation of HEI. Fields of study, the level of labor market demand for graduates, the material and technical base of higher education institutions, the infrastructure of the area where they are located are the factors of attracting students with high knowledge and training.

3. The educational process in HEIs. The quality composition of teaching professors and the organization of educational processes, methods and approaches for evaluating students' knowledge, the attitude of the management of HEIs to ensuring the quality of education.

4. Students' satisfaction with the educational environment of HEIs. Students' satisfaction with education is a factor that ensures the stable development of higher education institutions, and it is a means of improving the level of knowledge, culture and pedagogical skills of professors.

Therefore, the mission and strategic development directions of HEIs should be based on the systematic connection of components aimed at ensuring students' satisfaction with the educational environment.

Admission of a student to a higher educational institution instills confidence in one's own strength and abilities, hopes for a full and bright life. It is known that the educational process of the first year in a higher educational institution is the most complicated. Because the student has to comply with the internal procedures of the higher educational institution, which differ from the organizational point of view in the process of the secondary, secondary special and professional education system. In this case, the issue of the adaptation process between the requirements of the secondary, secondary special and professional education system and the requirements of the higher education system arises. At the moment, the effectiveness of ensuring the students' conscious attitude to education is more than equipped with modern material and technical tools, the existing comfortable pedagogical environment, the fact that the educational process is based on the needs of the students, with professors, teachers and fellow students. depends on factors such as relationships.

The analysis of scientific researches in our country affecting the satisfaction of students with the educational environment of HEIs, as well as with the professional activities of professors and teachers:

that it is related to factors such as slow social adaptation of students to new requirements in higher education after various educational institutions and lack of time to study at the required level;

difficulties in the process of adapting to new social conditions, lack of necessary pedagogical knowledge and skills, especially pedagogical tact of professors and teachers in class processes, insufficient objective approach in assessing the level of knowledge of students, educational content and spiritual-educational activities outside the audience made it possible to show cases such as not being directed to the needs of students, that is, the initiatives and opinions of students are not taken into account.

Most of the students show that they are not sufficiently satisfied with the educational environment, which in turn, under the influence of the studied indicators, decreases the educational motivation of students, self-evaluation, self-expression, during the study process. anxiety can increase the likelihood of stressful situations.

In our research, we have developed an evaluation technology based on indicators of student satisfaction in evaluating the activity of professors and teachers, and we have conducted a pilot test in HEIs designated as the object of research.

The main goals of evaluating the professional activity of professors and teachers based on the indicators of student satisfaction are as follows:

1. Identifying the main educational motives of students and indicators determining student satisfaction;
2. Improving the professional activity of professors and teachers by forming the conscious attitude of students towards education and the demand for the audience;
3. To determine the strengths and weaknesses of the educational process and the factors affecting the quality of education by analyzing the indicators of student satisfaction, as well as to eliminate the weak aspects of the educational process and the factors that have a negative impact determination of measures;
4. Development of a strategy for the development of the professional-pedagogical activities of professors and teachers at HEIs.

As part of our research, first of all, the opinions of students regarding the educational process at the Higher Education Institution were analyzed. 13.2% of the surveyed students admitted that the amount of assignments given to students is high, 21.3% of students stated that the amount of assignments was insufficient, 9.3% of the students' independent educational assignments 17.3% of students considered the volume and content of independent study assignments to be sufficient, 11.1% of students considered the imbalance of lectures and practical training, and 16.6% of students considered that assignments were distributed unevenly throughout the semester. admitted. Also, the following important trends reflecting the opinions of the respondents were identified: insufficient number of practice-oriented classes (31.6%), high weight of subjects of little importance for the specialty (10.6%), many final examinations encountering unfamiliar and extracurricular questions (23.8%).

When evaluating the activity of professors and teachers based on indicators of student satisfaction, we first studied the satisfaction of students with the educational environment, which is considered an important component of improving the quality of education, which affects the formation of the educational needs of the learner.

The questionnaire used the following questions:

1. How would you rate your level of satisfaction with your interactions with professors and teachers at the institution where you are studying?

2. How would you rate your level of satisfaction with your interactions with fellow students at the institution where you are studying?

3. How would you rate the level of attention paid to your initiatives and your satisfaction with their attention in the institution where you are studying?

4. How would you rate the level of satisfaction with the existing social, pedagogical and psychological environment (by the rector, faculty, heads of departments and teachers) in order to preserve the dignity of students in the institution where you are studying?

5. How would you rate your satisfaction with the comfort level of the environment in your educational institution for students?

6. How would you rate your level of satisfaction with the environment of respect for students (by the dean's office and professors) in the institution where you are studying?

7. How would you rate your level of satisfaction with the opportunity for students to receive help (from the rector, faculty, department heads and teachers, fellow students) at the institution where you are studying?

8. How would you rate the level of satisfaction with the opportunity for students to express their point of view on organizational and methodological issues of education at the institution where you are studying?

9. How would you rate the level of satisfaction of students with the opportunity to show initiative and activity in the institution where you are studying?

10. How would you rate your level of satisfaction with the consideration of students' personal problems and difficulties at the institution where you are studying?

11. How would you rate your level of satisfaction with the environment of helping students to make their own decisions at the institution where you are studying?

The following answers of the students to each question were taken into account: I am very satisfied (there is a full opportunity to help them make their own decision); I am mostly satisfied (the possibility of helping to choose one's own decision is mostly available); I am moderately

satisfied (in most cases, if not always, the opportunity to help one's decision is available); I am partially satisfied (help to choose one's own decision is partially available, but it is difficult to apply when necessary); I am not satisfied (it can be said that there is no possibility of helping to choose one's own decision); I am not satisfied at all (the possibility of helping to choose one's decision is not available at all).

The results of the survey conducted at the Kattakorgan branch of the Samarkand State University at the initial stage of experimental work were as follows.

Figure 1. The results of a survey conducted at the Kattakorgan branch of SamSU

Based on the obtained results, the influence of the organization of educational processes, the level of knowledge and culture of professors and teachers, pedagogical skills, support of students' initiatives, and approaches to evaluating student knowledge on student satisfaction was studied.

Within the framework of the World Bank's "Academic Innovation Fund" (AIF2/13) grant "Evaluation of Teacher Activity in Higher Education Institutions of Uzbekistan", the activity of professors and teachers at Samarkand State University in the course of the lesson and the satisfaction of students with this activity and their participation in higher educational institutions were investigated. Latent factors of the study and assessment of the relationship between the loyalty of children were identified (Table 1) [11].

Table 1. Brief description of latent factors

Factors		
Affecting factors	Professors and teachers:	Knowledge level and culture
		Pedagogical skills
		Student support
		Evaluation of students' knowledge
Resulting factors	Student satisfaction Loyalty of students to HEI	

The indicators for evaluating the professional activity of professors and teachers based on indicators of student satisfaction are presented in the following table:

Table 2. Indicators for evaluating the professional activity of professors and teachers based on indicators of student satisfaction (by influencing factors)

Latent factors	Indicators
Knowledge level and culture of teachers	The level of knowledge of teachers in their specialty The level of training Students' individual approach to learning To give knowledge in an organic and logical sequence. Level of spirituality and culture of professors and teachers Start and finish the lesson on time
Pedagogical skills of professors	Science explanation skills Lesson pace (speed) Creating conditions and encouraging students to freely express their opinions Organization of lessons based on interactivity. Use of modern pedagogical and information technologies Connecting the topic with other subjects and explaining it with practical examples.
Evaluation of students' knowledge	Advance notification of the method of assessment of students' knowledge Adherence to the criteria of justice in the assessment of students' knowledge. Avoiding cases of familiarity and arrogance in the assessment of students' knowledge. The method of assessing students' knowledge stimulates interest in learning.
Support of student initiatives	To give the right direction and support for the successful mastery of science It allows communication when necessary Sufficient help in case of a problem related to mastering science Providing sufficient and high-quality educational materials for mastering the subject. Mastery of science is constantly providing resources related to the subject

Based on these indicators, an electronic system aimed at evaluating the activity of professors and teachers was developed on the website of the Kattakorgan branch of Samarkand State University <http://samdukf.uz/anonim-sorovnom>.

As a result, rapid, step-by-step and periodical assessment was conducted by students.

At the next stage of our experimental work, the following results were obtained regarding the indicators of students' satisfaction with the educational environment (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The results of a survey conducted at the Kattakorgan branch of SamSU

According to the analysis of the results, rapid, step-by-step and periodic evaluation of the professional activity of professors and teachers based on the satisfaction of students, who are considered consumers of education, had a positive effect on the indicators of students' satisfaction with the educational environment of higher education institutions. That is, in the first survey, 52.8-66.3% of the students admitted that they were very satisfied, and in the subsequent stages, this indicator increased to 63.3-73.1%. Also, the weight of students who expressed dissatisfaction at all decreased from 1.6% to 0-0.3%.

In short, while recognizing that improving the quality of education in higher education institutions depends on the needs of learners, indicators of their satisfaction with the educational environment are one of the important components. The satisfaction of students with the educational environment of HEIs can be ensured, first of all, through the reputation of HEIs, as well as the level of knowledge and culture of professors and teachers, pedagogical skills, support for students' learning, and approaches to assessing students' knowledge.

Student satisfaction with education is a factor that ensures the stable development of HEIs and is an important tool in fulfilling the social order of society.

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